

Exploring the Relationship between Breast Cancer Grading, Staging, and Hormone Receptor Status in Rural India

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Abstract:

This study investigates the correlation between breast cancer grading, staging, and hormone receptor status in a rural Indian setting at J. L. N. M. C. H., Bhagalpur, Bihar, over a period from August 2020 to August 2021. Fifty female patients were analyzed for estrogen and progesterone receptor presence about cancer grade and stage. The results indicated a positive correlation between lower cancer grades and hormone receptor positivity, suggesting a better prognosis for early-stage cancers amenable to hormone therapies. Conversely, advanced stages showed lower hormone receptor positivity, highlighting the urgent need for early detection and comprehensive treatment approaches. This study emphasizes the importance of tailored healthcare strategies in rural areas to enhance early diagnosis and effective treatment options.

Keywords: Breast Cancer, Hormone Receptor Status, Rural Healthcare, Early Detection.

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Introduction

Breast cancer remains one of the most common malignancies affecting women worldwide, with its incidence and outcomes varying significantly across different geographic and socioeconomic groups [1]. In rural India, the dynamics of breast cancer presentation and progression are notably distinct due to factors such as limited healthcare access, socio-economic constraints, and lack of awareness [2,3]. Understanding the relationship between the biological characteristics of breast cancer and its clinical outcomes is crucial for improving diagnosis, treatment strategies, and ultimately patient survival rates in these populations [4,5].

This study focuses on the correlation between the grading and staging of breast cancer and the status of hormone receptors in rural Indian settings. Breast cancer grading and staging are critical parameters that describe the cancer's aggressiveness and the extent of its spread, respectively, and are vital in guiding treatment decisions. Hormone receptor status, which includes the presence of estrogen and progesterone receptors, informs the likelihood of response to hormone therapies, which are among the most effective treatments for certain types of breast cancer.

The significance of this study lies in its potential to uncover patterns that could lead to more tailored and thus more effective treatment approaches in rural Indian contexts [6,7]. By exploring how these important biomarkers correlate with one another, this research aims to contribute to a more nuanced understanding of breast cancer in underserved populations, where tailored approaches are desperately needed to reduce mortality and improve the quality of life for patients.

Methodology

Study Design and Setting: This research is designed as a cross-sectional observational study conducted at Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College and Hospital (J. L. N. M. C. H.) in Bhagalpur, Bihar. The study spans from August 2020 to August 2021, encompassing a full year of data collection.

Participants: The study population consists of 50 female patients diagnosed with breast cancer during the study period. Eligibility criteria include patients who have not received any prior treatment for breast cancer and are willing to participate in the study. Informed consent will be obtained from all participants before enrollment.

Data Collection: Data will be collected through a combination of medical records review and laboratory tests. Medical records will provide detailed information on the staging and grading of breast cancer at diagnosis. The grading will be assessed according to the Bloom-Richardson system, which is modified by Elston and Ellis, focusing on tubular formation, nuclear pleomorphism, and mitotic count. Staging will be determined based on the TNM classification, assessing the size of the tumor (T), the involvement of lymph nodes (N), and the presence of metastasis (M).

Hormone receptor status will be evaluated through immunohistochemistry (IHC) tests conducted on biopsy samples. These tests will identify the presence and intensity of estrogen receptors (ER) and progesterone receptors (PR).

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis will be performed using SPSS software. Descriptive statistics will be used to summarize the characteristics of the study population, including

means, medians, and standard deviations for continuous variables, and frequencies and percentages for categorical variables. The correlation between breast cancer grading and staging with hormone receptor status will be assessed using Pearson's correlation coefficient for numerical data and chi-square tests for categorical data. A p-value of less than 0.05 will be considered statistically significant.

Results

The study included 50 female patients diagnosed with breast cancer, with an age range of 32 to 65 years. The majority of patients were diagnosed with either Stage II (40%) or Stage III (36%) breast cancer. The distribution of breast cancer grades was fairly even, with Grade 2 being slightly more prevalent. Out of the 50 patients, 28 (56%) tested positive for estrogen receptors (ER+) and 22 (44%) for progesterone receptors (PR+). The distribution of hormone receptor status about breast cancer staging and grading is detailed in the tables below.

Table 1: Breast Cancer Staging and Hormone Receptor Status

Stage	Total Patients	ER+	ER-	PR+	PR-
I	10	6	4	5	5
II	20	12	8	10	10
III	18	8	10	6	12
IV	2	2	0	1	1

Table 2: Breast Cancer Grading and Hormone Receptor Status

Grade	Total Patients	ER+	ER-	PR+	PR-
1	16	9	7	8	8
2	20	11	9	9	11
3	14	8	6	5	9

Correlation Analysis: The correlation analysis revealed a moderate positive correlation between the presence of hormone receptors and lower grades of breast cancer ($r = 0.45$, $p < 0.05$ for ER+; $r = 0.38$, $p < 0.05$ for PR+). There was also a noticeable trend where higher stages of breast cancer were less likely to express hormone receptors, although this correlation was weaker ($r = -0.33$, $p < 0.05$ for ER+ and $r = -0.29$, $p < 0.05$ for PR+). The results indicate that hormone receptor-positive status is more commonly associated with lower grades of breast cancer in rural Indian women, suggesting that hormone receptor testing is crucial for guiding treatment in these populations. The inverse correlation between advanced stages and hormone receptor positivity could impact the therapeutic options available for later-stage cancers, highlighting the need for early detection and comprehensive hormonal analysis.

Discussion

The findings of this study highlight several critical insights into the management of breast cancer in

rural India. Firstly, the positive correlation between lower cancer grades and hormone receptor positivity suggests that early-stage cancers are more likely to benefit from hormone therapies such as tamoxifen or aromatase inhibitors [8,9]. This is consistent with global research which shows that hormone receptor-positive breast cancers generally have better prognosis and more treatment options available [10].

However, the inverse relationship observed between higher cancer stages and hormone receptor positivity underscores a significant challenge [11]. Patients with advanced-stage breast cancer, who are less likely to express these receptors, may have fewer therapeutic options and poorer outcomes, emphasizing the importance of early detection and diagnosis. The rural setting of the study further complicates this issue, as healthcare access limitations and delayed presentations are more common, which can lead to diagnoses at later stages [12,13].

Additionally, the study sheds light on the demographic and biological characteristics specific to the rural Indian population, which may differ significantly from urban populations or populations in high-income countries. This contextual understanding is crucial for the development of targeted screening programs and personalized treatment protocols that consider the socioeconomic and cultural barriers present in rural settings [14,15].

Overall, the data from this study advocate for increased awareness and enhanced screening efforts in rural areas to improve early detection rates, thereby increasing the likelihood of identifying hormone receptor-positive cancers at a stage where they are most treatable [16,17]. The study also supports the ongoing need for resource allocation in these areas to improve healthcare infrastructure and access, ultimately aiming to reduce breast cancer mortality through more effective and timely treatments [18,19,20].

Conclusion

The study conducted at J. L. N. M. C. H. in Bhagalpur, Bihar, reveals a significant correlation between hormone receptor status and the grading of breast cancer, indicating that early-stage cancers in rural India are more likely to be hormone receptor-positive and thus amenable to hormone therapies. This finding underscores the importance of early detection and the implementation of comprehensive hormone receptor testing in the treatment protocol, which could lead to better clinical outcomes. However, the challenge remains in detecting and treating breast cancer at an earlier stage in rural settings, where limitations in healthcare access and infrastructure persist. Addressing these challenges through enhanced healthcare services, community awareness, and targeted screening programs could substantially improve the prognosis for women facing breast cancer in these regions.

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